

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.1062 Max: 63.1962	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1245 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: ^{D 115-123} 1209, 1213 - Photo Model: Yes No #: 427

DEFINITION
western wall in room 5

Covered by SU: 1174 Fills ¹²⁴⁴ SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (frequent, (m)edium, (r)are)

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX					
☐ Pottery ☐ Nails ☐ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass	☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft </td> <td> ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify) </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Compaction	Color	☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft	☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: Is bound to (only for masonry): 1394

Is abutted by: 1217, 1231, 1187 Abuts: 1173

Is covered by: 1174, 5018 Covers:

Is cut by: 1175 Cuts:

Is filled by: Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
hot dry conditions, excavated with pickaxe + trowel

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: situated at the northwestern edge of area B 2010

Shape: linear

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: ☐ rounded ☐ straight</p> <p>Cut sides: ☐ straight ☐ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping</p> <p>Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☐ irregular</p> <p>How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded</p> <p>How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded</p> <p>Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p> <p>see back</p>
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: length: $15,40m$ (after complete exposure in 2011) $7,30m$ width: $0,39m$ height: $0,65m$

Description: The ashlar wall appeared beneath SU wall 1058 and was hollowed out for the construction of 1058 by cut 1175.

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

westernmost wall of the excavated property, running N-S, the wall consists mainly of ashlar but there are some tiles and some irregular tufo blocks used within it. Wall 1245 seems to represent the original retaining wall of the house in Trench B.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by **CHM**

Revised by **CHM**

PDFd by **EIR**

Entered by

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on